

PROBLEMS IN READING COMPREHENSION OF THE SELECTED THIRD YEAR BAELS STUDENTS OF MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

Fadzner J. Jhun, Rosana S. Yusop, Malangka A. Hasirul, Sherfa K. Muay,
Sakur S. Kamlon, Farrah Carlson L. Tandih

Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191671>

ABSTRACT

This research endeavored to present the problems of the chosen respondents in terms of their problems in reading comprehension. It has the following objectives: 1. To identify the problems in reading comprehension of the selected third year BA ELS students, 2. To ascertain the common hindrances that can affect the interest of the selected third year BA ELS students in reading comprehension, and 3. To present an ideal way for the selected third year BA ELS students to improve their reading comprehension. This research presented the following results: The selected third year BA ELS students' problems in reading comprehension are, namely: lack of vocabularies, lack of interest, and leaping of pages. The survey showed that the level of problems of the selected third year BA ELS students in reading comprehension based on sub-statements are: Lack of vocabularies, which ranked first; Leaping of pages, which ranked second; and Lack of interest, which got the third rank. Additionally, the common barriers that most of the selected third year BA ELS students had encountered are: Friends, social media, gadgets, neighbor, sleepy and stress, laziness, works, lack of motivation, encountering confusing words, and tired and hungry. Moreover, the ideal way to improve their reading comprehension, as affirmed by the respondents are the following: Reading every day, reading more books, watching movies (preferably English), reading more often, analyzing well the contents of the different reading texts, and consulting the dictionary for the unfamiliar terms. It is, therefore, recommended that to be able to comprehend the context of any writings, the BA ELS students, and any other students, must be motivated enough to improve their comprehension; the BA ELS students, and any other students, should heighten their interest in reading; since lack of vocabularies is one of the problem, reading comprehension must be given focus; lastly, there must be enough printed materials provided in school, so that BA ELS students, and any other students, will have enough source of information and more reading avenues.

Keywords: *Reading comprehension, vocabularies, interest, motivation, laziness, confusing words*

INTRODUCTION

People learn comprehension skills through education or instruction while some learn by direct experiences. Proficient reading depends on the ability to recognize words quickly and effortlessly. It is also determined by an individual's cognitive development, which is "the construction thought processes". According to Zimmerman and Hutchins (2003), real reading has to do with thinking, learning, and expanding a reader's knowledge and horizons. It has to do with building on past knowledge, mastering new information, and connecting with the minds of those you have never met. Comprehension relies on two, interconnected words: word reading (being able to decode the symbols on the page) and language comprehension (being able to understand the meaning of the words and sentences) (Compton, 2003).

There are specific characteristics that determined how successfully an individual will comprehend text, including prior knowledge about the subject, well-developed language, and the ability to make inferences from methodical questioning and monitoring comprehension like; "Why is important?" and "Do I need to read the entire text?" are examples of passage questioning (Al-Jarrah and Ismail, 2018).

Reading comprehension is the ability to process text, understand its meaning, and to integrate with what the reader already knows. Fundamental skills required in efficient reading comprehension are knowing meaning of words, ability to understand meaning of a word from discourse context, ability to follow organization of passage and to identify antecedents and references in it, ability to draw inferences from a passage about its contents, ability to identify the main thought of a passage, ability to answer questions answered in a passage, ability to recognize the literary devices or propositional structures used in a passage and determine its tone, to understand the situational mood (agents, objects, temporal and spatial reference points, casual and intentional inflections, etc.) conveyed for assertions, questioning, commanding, refraining etc., and finally, ability to determine writer's purpose, intent and point of view, and draw inferences about the writer (discourse-semantics) (Newmark, 2004).

Without proper comprehension skills, students lack the ability to understand what they read. The point of reading isn't to make sounds in your brain or out loud, but rather, to understand important lesson, stories and arguments. Through the act of writing, our ancestors have recorded important knowledge that we can understand simply by reading. By understanding what we read, we pick up important information, understand scientific theories, past opinions and new frontiers. (in layman's terms, it is through reading that we no longer have to 'discover' gravity, or the independence of 182 nations with every new generation).

Having excellent reading comprehensions skills is crucial. It increases the enjoyment and effectiveness of reading and helps not only academically, but professionally, and in a person's personal life (William, 2009).

Most of the students are not aware that they are already eliminating some strategy to understand the whole context. As the observation of the researchers many students who struggled with reading so much, that they focus all their energy on decoding words, and hardly notice the content of what they are reading. Even a reader who is fairly fluent may not pay proper attention to content while reading. Basically, all of the articles are needed to be analyzed to get the main point. Thus, reading comprehension is the basic way to understand the ideas of the texts. It helps the readers to have the connotative meaning of the words or sentences. The students do not just know the meaning of a single word but rather the meaning behind it. If the students can comprehend what was written on the page it will help them to build their self-esteem and boost their psychological well-being.

In the reasons aforesaid, the researchers observed that these problems are existing among the selected third year students of Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies (BA ELS).

Research Questions:

This research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the problems in reading comprehension of the selected third year BAELS Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?
2. What are the common hindrances that can affect the interest of the selected third year BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in reading comprehension?
3. What is the ideal way for the selected third year BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu to improve their reading comprehension?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the campus of Mindanao State University-Sulu at Capitol Hills, Jolo, Sulu, specifically, in the College of Arts and Sciences. The said college was established in 1974 and was located at the Capitol site, Jolo, Sulu. The main building could be found between the Administration Building and the College of Biology.

Sampling Design

This study used Simple Random Sampling in the selection of respondents. In selecting the data to be studied, the researchers selected only thirty (30) students from the total number of the third year BAELS students enrolled in Mindanao State University-Sulu Academic Year 2021-2022.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the selected third year BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu who were officially enrolled in the first semester of academic year 2021-2022.

Data Gathering Procedure

In conducting the study, the researchers complied the following steps: First, problems that could affect the interest of the students in reading were identified. Second, the respondents preferred were the selected third year BA ELS Students academic year 2021-2022. Third, questions to grant possible answers to the problems were constructed. Fourth, the researchers inquired and looked for information related to the study in printed materials and in internet. Lastly, after gathering the data from various sources, the researchers chose the most applicable data which made up the whole content of the researchers.

Research Instrument

In this research, survey questionnaire, was formulated and an interview was conducted during data gathering process. The questions derived from the dominant focus of the problem. The survey questionnaire directed on the problems in reading comprehension of the selected third year BAELS students' academic year 2021-2022. This study used descriptive-survey method as the research design. According to Creswell (2009), the descriptive research design is a study that describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studies, primarily used to gain an understanding of a group or phenomenon. This involves collecting data through surveys, interviews, or observation. This design answers "Who, What, When, Where, Why, and How."

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This study focused on identifying problems in reading comprehension of the selected third year BAELS students. Thus, it is limited also to determining the problem of Reading Comprehension of the said respondents and their profile. The respondents were the selected third year BAELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu who are officially enrolled in the first semester Academic Year 2021-2022.

RESULTS

Participants' Profile

Table 1.1

Age	Frequency	%
30	1	3.33%
26	1	3.33%
25	1	3.33%
24	1	3.33%
23	3	10%
22	8	26.67%
21	11	36.67%
20	3	10%
19	1	3.33%
Total	N = 30	99.99%

Table 1.2

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	6	20%
Female	24	80%
Total	30	100%

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

In terms of age, as reflected in Table 1.1, eleven (11) of the selected third year BA ELS students, served as the majority which belongs to 21 years old and covering 36.67% of the total respondents. Eight (8) of them, belonged to the age of 22, taking 26.67% of the total respondents. Then, belonging to the age of 23, which is three (3) of them covered the 10% of the total respondents, same as those who belonged to age 20, which is also three (3), and similarly taking 10% of the total respondents. The remaining five (5) respondents were composed of different ages: 19, 24, 25, 26, and 30, which covered 16.67% of the total respondents.

In terms of gender, as shown in Table 1.2, 20% of the total respondents are male, comprising six (6) respondents. Then twenty-four (24) of them are female, which covered 80% of the total respondents.

Problems of Selected Third Year BAELS Students in Reading Comprehension

Table 2.1

Problems	Frequency					(W _x) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
Lack of Vocabularies	0	6	10	12	2	2.67	Low	1
Lack of Interest	0	7	6	11	6	2.47	Very Low	2
Leaping of Pages	2	1	7	19	1	2.47	Very Low	2
Grand Mean = 2.54						Low		

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 2.1 presents the problems of selected third year BA ELS students in reading comprehension. It consists of five (5) responses provided in the questionnaire. In solving the weighted mean, the researchers got the number of students who answered in a particular choice or item, then multiplied it to its corresponding scale or equivalent rate, then divided it by the total number of the respondents. After the weighted mean was determined, the study revealed that 90% of the respondents showed **Low** response in terms of the problems presented.

Thus, the survey revealed that the respondents that majority of the third year BAELS students of the said university do not significantly possess the problems presented.

To obtain the rank, the highest average score was used. As presented in the table, the problem in their reading comprehension - Lack of Vocabularies - ranked first, which it is their main problem in reading comprehension. This is followed by the Lack of Interest, which tied with the Leaping of Pages.

Table 2.2

Female

Problems	Frequency					(W _x) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
Lack of Vocabularies	1	4	9	10	0	2.83	Low	1
Lack of Interest	1	6	4	9	4	2.63	Low	2
Leaping of Pages	2	0	4	16	2	2.33	Very Low	3
Grand Mean = 2.60							Low	

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 2.2 showed the problems of the respondents, specifically in the female category. The table revealed that the items showed **Low** grand mean, which implied that the female respondents do not have problems at all in terms of their reading comprehension. Table 2.1 and Table 2.2 showed analogous results. The category *Lack of Vocabularies* ranked first with the average weighted mean of 2.83 and interpreted as “Low” which means that the female of the respondents possessed enough vocabularies for them to understand what they read. The category *Lack of Interest* ranked second with the average weighted mean of 2.63 and interpreted as “Low,” which means that the female of the respondents was have always an interest to read. Last in rank is the category *Leaping of Pages* with the mean of 2.33 and interpreted as “Very Low.”

Table 2.3

Male

Problems	Frequency					(W _x) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
Lack of Vocabularies	0	1	0	3	2	2	Very Low	3
Lack of Interest	0	2	2	0	2	2.67	Low	2
Leaping of Pages	1	0	2	3	0	2.83	Low	1
Grand Mean = 2.5 Very Low								

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 2.3 showed the problems of the respondents, specifically in the male category. The table revealed that the items implied a **Very Low** interpretation. The category *Leaping of Pages* ranked first, with the average weighted mean of 2.83 and interpreted as “Low” which means that the male respondents were not too lazy in reading. The category *Lack of Interest* ranked second, with the average weighted mean of 2.67 and interpreted as “Low” which means that the male respondents have much interest in reading. And the category *Lack of Vocabularies* ranked third, with the average weighted mean of 2 and interpreted as “Very Low” which means that the male respondents have enough vocabularies with them.

Furthermore, Table 2.2 (female respondents) and Table 2.3 (male respondents) showed difference in ranks in terms of the following category: lack of vocabularies, lack of interest, and leaping of pages. *Lack of Vocabularies* ranked first among female respondents, while it ranked third among the male respondents. *Leaping of Pages* ranked third among the female respondents, while it ranked first among the male respondents. In the *Lack of Interest*, which is ranked second, both female and male respondents fall in the same level.

Level of the Problems of the Selected Third Year BAELS Students in Reading Comprehension

The succeeding tables in this section showed the level of the problems in reading comprehension of the selected third year BA ELS students of Mindanao State University – Sulu. The level was categorized and explained into three tables. The researchers applied weighted mean as their statistical tool in order to determine the level of problems in each category.

Table 3.1

Lack of Vocabularies	Frequency					(Wx) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
A. Confusing words	0	10	14	2	4	3.13	Low	1
B. Unfamiliar Words	4	1	16	8	1	2.97	Low	2
C. Length and complexity of words	1	4	15	10	0	2.87	Low	3
D. Limitation of source of information about words	0	4	15	5	6	2.57	Low	4
E. No comprehension at all	1	1	10	14	4	2.37	Very Low	5
Gen. Mean = 2.79								Low

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 3.1 presents the *Lack of Vocabularies* category. The table revealed that most of the items or sub-categories showed **Low** description. The item *Confusing Words* ranked first, with the average weighted mean of 3.13 and interpreted as “Low,” which means that the respondents were good enough in terms of possessing vocabulary that relates to the words that have multiple meanings. Then, the *Unfamiliar Words* ranked second with the average weighted mean of 2.97, also interpreted as “Low,” which means that majority of the respondents have familiarity with most of the words that they encounter in different reading materials. The *Length and Complexity of Words* ranked third with the average weighted mean of 2.87 and also interpreted as “Low,” which means

that the respondents were also good in terms of understanding the meaning of words that are spelled long and difficult to pronounce. The *Limitation of Source of Information about Words* ranked fourth with the average weighted mean of 2.57, is also interpreted as “Low,” which means that the respondents have enough source of information on the meanings of words. And the sub-category *No Comprehension at All* ranked fifth with the average weighted mean of 2.37 and interpreted as “Very low,” which means that the respondents can comprehend well the context of any writings or texts.

Table 3.2

Lack of Interest	Frequency					(Wx) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
A. I choose social media over books	2	5	12	8	3	2.68	Low	1
B. Lack of concentration when reading books	1	4	8	12	5	2.33	Very Low	2
C. Lack of motivation	0	4	8	10	8	2.27	Very Low	3
D. I need a reason to read	1	5	7	6	11	2.3	Very Low	4
E. Slow Reader	0	3	2	5	20	1.6	No Problem at All	5
Gen. Mean = 2.23						Very Low		

<i>Legend:</i>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 3.2 presents the *Lack of Interest* category. The table revealed that most of the items implied **Very Low** as reflected in the range of interpretation. The statement *I choose social media over books* ranked first with the average weighted mean of 2.68 interpreted as “Low,” which means that the respondents do not totally focus on social media over reading books. It was followed by the item *Lack of Concentration when Reading Books* ranked second with the average weighted mean of 2.33 interpreted as “Very Low,” which means that the respondents have been providing much concentration in terms of reading. The *Lack of Motivation* ranked third with the average weighted mean of 2.27, interpreted as “Very Low,” which means the respondents were motivated enough to read. The item *I Need a Reason* to read ranked fourth with the average weighted mean

of 2.3, interpreted as “Very Low,” which means that the respondents were not totally in need of any possible reasons to read. And lastly, *Slow Reader* ranked fifth with the average weighted mean of 1.6, and interpreted as “No Problem at All,” which means that the respondents were fast enough in reading.

Table 3.3

Leaping of Pages	Frequency					(Wx) MEAN	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
A. I have too much else to do	1	5	10	8	6	2.57	Low	1
B. I don't like the context of the story	1	1	11	14	3	2.43	Very Low	2
C. I always fall into a sleepy mood	1	1	5	17	6	2.13	Very Low	3
D. Reading is not my habit	0	3	6	13	8	2.13	Very Low	3
E. Reading is boring	0	2	6	11	11	1.97	Very Low	4
Gen. Mean = 2.25							Very Low	

Legend:	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Descriptive Interpretation</u>
	5	4.50-5.00	Very High
	4	3.50-4.49	High
	3	2.50-3.49	Low
	2	1.50-2.49	Very Low
	1	1.00-1.49	Least Problem

Table 3.3 presents the *Leaping of Pages*' category. The table revealed that most of the items showed the **Very Low** measure in terms of interpretation. The sub-category *I have too much else to do* ranked first with the average weighted mean of 2.57 and interpreted as “Low,” which means that the respondents did not really prioritize many tasks other than reading. The sub-category *I don't like the context of the story* ranked second with the average weighted mean of 2.43 and interpreted as “Very Low,” which means that the respondents liked the contents of any texts they read. This was followed by the items *I always fall into a sleepy mood* and *Reading is not my habit*, which took the same ranked as third with the average weighted mean of 2.13 and interpreted as “Very Low,” which means both were not really the problem of the respondents in connection to reading; they always loved to read and gave their attention to whatever they read. Then, the sub-category *Reading is boring* ranked fifth with the average weighted of 1.97 and interpreted as “Very Low,” which means that the respondents enjoyed reading.

The researchers also conducted an interview with the selected third year BA ELS students in order to answer the problem number three (3) which is "What are barriers to the respondents' reading comprehension?"

To be able to gather answers from the respondents, the researchers interviewed them one by one using the following questions:

1. Is there any voracious reader in your family or at your home?
2. Is there any reading material at your home?
3. Do you read? How often?
4. If you read, do you comprehend it easily?

5. What is/are actually the most common barrier/s that lost your interest in reading?
6. What do you think is the ideal way to improve your reading comprehension?

After the interview the researchers found out the following answers:

1. Ninety percent (90%) or twenty-seven (27) of the thirty students declared that there are voracious readers in their family.
2. All of the respondents claimed that they have reading materials at home.
3. All of the respondents affirmed that they read every day. But twenty-four of them said that they do not read often. Few of the professed that they read twice or three times per week.
4. Seventy percent (70%) or 21 of the respondents affirmed that they can easily comprehend what they read. And the remaining thirty percent (30%) or 9 of the respondents acknowledged that they cannot easily comprehend what they read.
5. Friends, social media, gadgets, neighbor, sleepy and stress, lazy, works, lack of motivation, encounter confusing words, tired and hungry were the answers of the respondents when they were asked about the most common barrier/s that affect their interest in reading.
6. Majority of the respondents answered that their ideal way to improve their reading comprehension are the following: Read every day, read more books, watch movies, read more often, analyze well the contents of the different reading texts, and consult the dictionary for the unfamiliar terms.

Conclusions

The first problem in reading comprehension of the selected third year BAELS students is the *lack of vocabularies*, since vocabulary is the key to reading comprehension. Readers cannot understand what they are reading without knowing what most of the words mean. Secondly, the *leaping of pages* also existed as one of the problems since reading should involve attention and focus, which some of the respondents did not possess. Lastly, *lack of interest* also appeared as a problem if the readers cannot comprehend what they read.

It can also be concluded that the social media can affect the readers' focus and interest, and concentration, considering reading as one of the boring tasks to do, especially for the young generation.

Moreover, from the answers of the respondents in relation to the common barriers to reading, the researchers could resolve on the idea that friends, gadgets, social media, and the environment could greatly influence the interest in reading of the young people.

Recommendations

1. It is suggested that to be able to comprehend the context of any writings, the BAELS students, and any other students, must be motivated enough to improve their comprehension and that will start from their selves.
2. It is recommended that the BAELS students, and any other students, should heighten their interest in reading.
3. Since lack of vocabularies is one of the problems, reading comprehension must be given focus.
4. It is also recommended that there must be enough printed materials provided in school, so that BAELS students, and any other students, will have enough source of information and more reading avenues.
5. It is also recommended that the BAELS students, and any other students, should engage themselves into any activities pertaining to Public Speaking.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors have declared that they have no conflicting interests in relation to the research, composition, or publication of this work. The writers conducted the investigation in accordance with the research ethical protocol. The participant gave their informed consent before to receiving the study's survey. The highest level of confidentiality was observed in the data management process.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express their sincere gratitude and appreciation to everyone who helped make this work successful and who provided them with support and direction.

First and foremost, they are incredibly appreciative to the Almighty Allah SWT for His generosity and for bestowing upon them the positive and, above all, perseverance needed to finish the assignment on schedule.

They are extremely appreciative to Dr. Nagder J. Abdurahman, the vibrant chancellor of Mindanao State University-Sulu, for giving them authorization to conduct this study there.

They also extend their warm gratitude to College of Arts and Sciences Dean Prof. Ajid M. Sari for his help and support.

Lastly, they would like to express their sincere gratitude to their family members for their unwavering support and fervent prayers throughout. Their families have shown them unending love and support, which has fueled their desire to finish this study.

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